

Analysis of Basic Needs Factors Affecting the Academic Success of Affirmation Students: A Case Study at Jenderal Soedirman University

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the factors influencing the academic success of ADIK Papua affirmation students, particularly at Jenderal Soedirman University, using Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory. The research aims to understand how the fulfillment of psychological, social, and self-actualization needs impacts the adaptation and academic achievements of affirmation students. Employing a qualitative descriptive approach, this study surveyed 12 recipients of the ADIK Papua scholarship from various faculties and departments at Jenderal Soedirman University. Data were collected through observations and open-ended questionnaires, analyzed using an interactive three-step model: data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing with verification. The findings reveal that the fulfillment of basic needs, including security, social support, and self-actualization, significantly influences the adaptation and academic success of ADIK Papua affirmation students.

KEYWORDS: Academic Success, Affirmation Students, Needs Theory.

INTRODUCTION

According to Indonesia's Central Statistics Agency (BPS), the Human Development Index (HDI) in Papua stood at 63.01% in 2023, significantly lower than other regions, such as Sleman Regency, which reached 84.86% the same year. Papua is home to the highest number of 3T (Outermost, Frontier, and Underdeveloped) areas in Indonesia [1, 2]. This makes Papua a focal point for improving human resource quality, particularly to enhance its contribution to national development [1, 3]. Education is a critical avenue for achieving this objective, with evidence showing that educational and training investments positively influence economic growth [4, 5]. Research highlights that low education levels correlate with higher regional unemployment rates [6].

The government's strategy to accelerate education is outlined in Article 56 of Law No. 21 of 2001 on Papua's special autonomy, which guarantees every citizen's right to quality education at the lowest possible cost. One manifestation of this mandate is the Affirmation Higher Education Scholarship Program (ADIK), designed to provide access for high school graduates from underdeveloped regions with limited educational infrastructure to state universities without the regular selection process [7]. This initiative is a strategic step toward building local capacity and fostering sustainable positive impacts [8]. However, the program also presents unique challenges for students, as they must leave their home regions and adapt to new educational environments vastly different from their origins [9]. Research by Arsyad, et al. [10], highlights difficulties such as limited understanding of chosen study programs, which undermines learning motivation. Cultural and language barriers in educational communication also pose significant challenges [11].

Observations at Jenderal Soedirman University reveal that affirmation students from Papua often have distinctive dialects, which hinder effective communication with peers. This can negatively impact academic performance, necessitating adaptation efforts. Students must navigate cultural and social differences, requiring tolerance and intercultural communication skills to integrate into new environments [12]. Adapting to new circumstances is never easy, as it requires individuals to learn and navigate through various differences [13]. Unfamiliar settings can lead to lower academic achievement and completion rates [14]. Conversely, supportive campus environments fulfill students' psychological needs, intrinsically motivating them to excel academically [15]. Support for fulfilling basic needs is a crucial strategy for enhancing academic success on university campuses [14, 16].

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory identifies five basic human needs—physiological, safety, social, esteem, and self-actualization—emphasizing their sequential fulfillment [17, 18]. Key components such as safety, psychological support, and self-actualization are critical motivational factors for achieving academic goals [19]. Rahmadania and Aly [20] found that Maslow's theory enhances both learning motivation and educational outcomes. Environmental motivation is particularly crucial for students

in fulfilling their needs, including the pursuit of knowledge [21]. However, the implementation of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory to analyze the factors influencing the academic success of affirmation students has not yet been explored. This theory is valuable for understanding whether the basic needs of ADIK Papua affirmation students are being fulfilled within the university environment to support their academic achievements.

This study offers a novel contribution to the application of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory in understanding the academic success of ADIK Papua affirmation students at Jenderal Soedirman University. It also examines the role of motivation arising from the fulfillment of basic needs within their environment in enhancing the academic performance of affirmation students. The orientation of the university environment is directed toward helping new students familiarize themselves with their academic surroundings [12]. Furthermore, the focus on ADIK Papua affirmation students provides insights into the cross-cultural relevance of motivational theory, particularly regarding the fulfillment of needs for students from diverse cultural backgrounds.

Therefore, based on the background, issues, preliminary studies, and novelty presented in this research, it is crucial to analyze the factors affecting the academic success of ADIK Papua affirmation students at Jenderal Soedirman University using Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory. This study aims to understand how the fulfillment of psychological, social, and self-actualization needs among affirmation students impacts their adaptation and academic achievements.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative descriptive approach using a case study method to analyze the fundamental factors influencing students' academic success. The case study method involves in-depth exploration of specific programs, processes, or activities relevant to the research subjects [22]. The research was conducted at Jenderal Soedirman University, which has been collaborating with ADIK students since 2022. The research subjects consisted of 12 ADIK Papua scholarship recipients, spread across various faculties and departments at Jenderal Soedirman University. The subjects were selected randomly, ensuring comprehensive representation despite the limited population size.

Case studies are bounded by time and activity, with data collection conducted in detail through various procedures over a continuous period. The qualitative research procedure utilizing the case study method was adapted from Creswell and Clark [23] dan Creswell [24], comprising several key stages: (1) case selection and problem formulation; (2) data collection; (3) data analysis; (4) data triangulation; and (5) report writing and conclusion drawing. This study aims to analyze the factors influencing the academic success of ADIK Papua affirmative students at Jenderal Soedirman University. Data were collected using observation techniques and open-ended questionnaires filled out by the students. The use of open-ended questionnaires was intended to obtain in-depth and diverse responses, enabling the researcher to understand the students' perspectives, thoughts, and experiences comprehensively.

Data analysis was conducted using Miles and Huberman [25], interactive analysis model, which consists of three main steps: (1) data reduction, involving sorting, selecting, and grouping relevant information to structure the data for further analysis; (2) data display, where reduced data is presented in an easily comprehensible format such as tables, matrices, or descriptive narratives; and (3) conclusion drawing and verification, where conclusions are verified by comparing them with existing data to achieve strong and accurate interpretations. These three steps were carried out interactively and continuously throughout the research process to ensure in-depth and valid analysis results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The initial analysis phase revealed that the basic needs emphasized by ADIK Papua affirmative students are aligned with three aspects: security, psychological support, and a sense of acceptance within Jenderal Soedirman University's environment. Based on observations and the responses from the students' open-ended questionnaires, those who felt psychologically secure and received adequate social support from peers and lecturers demonstrated higher learning motivation. Psychological and functional support plays a crucial role in enhancing students' academic motivation, thereby increasing their engagement and resilience in an academic environment [26, 27]. Support from peers and educators significantly impacts students' motivation and involvement in their academic environment [28]. These basic factors align with Maslow's hierarchy of needs, which has proven vital for ADIK Papua affirmative students to overcome the challenges of adapting to a new environment.

A. Security Factors

This study found that Papua affirmative students felt calmer and more adaptable when the campus environment offered protection from discrimination and supported cultural diversity. The security factor encompassed both physical and psychological aspects, such as adequate facilities, a friendly social environment, and campus policies that safeguard their rights and well-being. The need for security involves a sense of protection from potential risks [21]. The results of the security factor analysis are presented graphically in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Security Factor Analysis Results

Based on Figure 1, most ADIK Papua affirmative students reported feeling safe or very safe within the environment of Jenderal Soedirman University. Students stated that their sense of safety and comfort increased over time, thanks to the support they received from senior students in organizations and academic advisors. Educators play a crucial role in enhancing learning through motivational support [29]. They must create environments that foster learning motivation [19]. Another reason for their sense of safety was the presence of security personnel assigned across the campus, which students found helpful. Campus safety and security relate to facilities that help mitigate instability within the academic environment [30].

Maslow's motivation theory suggests that security encompasses both physical and psychological aspects. To further explore this, the study analyzed whether students had experienced teasing or bullying. One student mentioned encountering verbal teasing from peers, which diminished their comfort due to feelings of disrespect. Students who feel free from stigma or prejudice show more active engagement in academic and non-academic activities [14, 15]. However, the student responded positively, avoiding negative reactions, which prevented recurrence and maintained social stability [31]. Psychological security is especially crucial for affirmative students, as they come from diverse social backgrounds and require support to adapt to the new academic environment.

B. Social Support Factors

This research indicated that positive social interactions on campus play a vital role in the academic success of Papua affirmative students. Participation in student organizations, study groups, and campus activities helped them feel accepted as part of the academic community. Table 1 presents the results of the analysis of various aspects measuring social support factors that influence the academic success of ADIK Papua students at Jenderal Soedirman University.

Ryan and Deci [32] identified two critical factors influencing academic motivation: learner-related characteristics and social factors (activities, peers, courses, tasks, or environment). This study found that students active in social activities and campus organizations felt more motivated to excel and better able to overcome learning obstacles such as language difficulties or cultural adaptation. Social support provides students with opportunities to communicate, share experiences, and build networks with peers from diverse backgrounds, fostering a sense of community and boosting confidence in achieving academic goals. Supportive communication with family and peers further nurtures this development [33]. Support activities extend beyond academic endeavors to include various extracurricular activities [26].

Table 1. Social Support Factor Analysis Results

Questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Participating in social activities in the surrounding environment	58%	25%	17%	0%
Having close friends within the campus community	66%	17%	17%	0%
Joining organizations or committees on campus	75%	8%	17%	0%
Having a support system during college	58%	17%	25%	0%

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ADIK Papua affirmative students highlighted peer support as a primary source of motivation. Friends who understood their challenges encouraged them to stay motivated in their studies. Additionally, support from Papua student communities or similar organizations offered emotional comfort and extra motivation. Peer-driven motivation is critical for meeting students' basic learning needs [21]. Some students also mentioned that lecturers open to cultural discussions made them feel valued and comfortable. Consistent with the findings of Goodwin, et al. [34], educator-student interactions through in-depth activities and communication promote personal development, academic mentoring, and other developmental activities.

C. Self-Actualization Factors

Self-actualization represents the highest level in Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, where individuals achieve their full potential and strive to be the best version of themselves [35]. Those who attain self-actualization exhibit high creativity, independence, self-acceptance, and a strong commitment to meaningful goals, both personal and societal [36]. The analysis results of self-actualization factors among ADIK Papua affirmative students are presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Analysis Results of Self-Actualization Factors

Questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Completing assignments ahead of time	67%	25%	8%	0%
Active participation in learning activities	50%	42%	8%	0%
Enthusiastic engagement in learning	75%	25%	0%	0%
Satisfactory academic performance (GPA)	92%	8%	0%	0%

Based on the analysis in Table 1, most ADIK Papua affirmative students at Jenderal Soedirman University demonstrated high motivation and engagement in academic activities. Specifically, 67% of students strongly agreed that they completed assignments ahead of deadlines, 50% strongly agreed that they were actively involved in learning activities, and 75% expressed a high level of enthusiasm for participating in classes. These findings indicate that the majority of students effectively manage their time, which is a critical aspect of self-actualization. Time management is an essential element for students to enhance academic achievement [37]. The university environment, active involvement in organizations, and enthusiasm for learning simultaneously have a significant impact on academic performance [38]. The high percentages observed reflect students' positive attitudes and active participation in class activities.

Grade point average (GPA) serves as one measure of academic success. This study found that nearly all students were satisfied with their GPA achievements. Consistent with the findings of Septiani and Purwanto [39], there is a positive relationship between self-confidence and learning outcomes. Therefore, it can be concluded that the self-actualization needs of Papua affirmative students are being adequately fulfilled, contributing positively to their academic success.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The fulfillment of basic needs for ADIK Papua affirmative students, encompassing security factors, social support, and self-actualization, plays a crucial role in facilitating their adaptation and academic success at Jenderal Soedirman University. The need for safety, coupled with social support from peers, educators, and an inclusive campus environment, enhances students' learning motivation and engagement in both academic and non-academic activities. Furthermore, the self-actualization needs reflected in intrinsic motivation to achieve academic excellence indicate their ability to manage time effectively and express satisfaction with their academic achievements. By identifying the supporting factors for academic success based on Maslow's hierarchy of needs, as presented in this study, it is recommended that the university strengthens environmental orientation programs, provides adequate social and psychological support, and fosters a safe environment that values the cultural diversity of affirmative students. These efforts will ensure sustainable support for their academic success.

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